

COMPETENCES IN THE PREPARATION OF FUTURE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Educational technology is a system of joint activities of students and teachers in the design (planning), organization, orientation and adjustment of the educational process in order to achieve a specific result while providing comfortable conditions for participants.

The competence approach is defined through the interpretation of the concepts of "competence" and "competency".

Competence is defined as:

1) The ability to do something well or effectively; 2) Compliance with the requirements for employment; 3) The ability to perform special work functions.

Competence means thorough knowledge in a particular field.

The subject "English" has a great potential for the formation of key competencies.

General principles of the competence approach:

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the competences of the training of future English teachers, which are covered by the principles of the competency approach.

- The purpose of education is to develop students' ability to make independent decisions based on their experience.
- The content of the training is the actions and operations that relate to the skills that you need to get.
- It is necessary to create conditions for the formation of students' experience of self-solving problems.
- The assessment of learning outcomes is based on the analysis of the level of education achieved by students, e.g. at the level of their competencies.

Simply put, knowledge in training ceases to play a major role. Knowledge is certainly important, but the main task of education is to teach the student to use this knowledge to solve various problems.

✓ Learn to learn, that is, learn to determine the goals of cognitive activity, choose sources of information, find the best ways to achieve the goal, evaluate the results and independently organize their activities.

✓ Learn to explain the phenomena of reality, their essence and causes, using the appropriate scientific apparatus.

✓ Learn to navigate the key issues of our time (economy, politics, intercultural interaction, etc.).

✓ Learn to navigate the world of spiritual values.

✓ Learn to solve problems related to the implementation of various social roles.

✓ Learn to solve problems common to different types of professional activities.

In this way, learning takes on an entirely new form. The principles laid down in the competence approach should eventually train independent, self-confident individuals. Individuals who have sufficient competencies for later life, for self-realization and disclosure of their potential. Therefore, I began to introduce the methods and forms of the competence approach into my practice.

General concept of the competence approach

According to the classification of A.V. Khutorsky, there are 3 main types of competencies:

— key competencies: value-semantic, general cultural, educational and cognitive, informational, communicative, social and labor, competence of personal improvement;

— general subject competencies;

— subject competencies.

The main means of forming key competencies in the study of a foreign language are various technologies, forms and methods. There are no completely incompetent forms and methods of educational work. But some forms themselves do not work for the development of key competencies:

1. teacher's monologue;

2. front-end individual survey;
3. informative conversations;
4. independent work with the textbook on the tasks of the teacher;
5. film demonstration;
6. traditional control work.

Competence-based methods are those that have not only educational, but also life justification. These are:

- problematization of content in the context of today's and tomorrow's life of students;
- organization of extracurricular activities.

Use of competence-based methods and forms of teaching:

- a) project method;
- b) developing critical thinking;
- c) the method of debate;
- d) game technology (language, role-playing games, dramatization);
- e) case study;
- f) Problematic discussions;
- g) pair and group work;
- h) language portfolio;
- i) use of audio-visual means, multimedia technologies, Internet resources.

Competence-based methods and forms of training

Discussions, conversations, role-playing games of a problem orientation, project activities-these are the types of activities that encourage students to think independently in oral or written form.

We will discuss in more detail some of the competence-based methods and forms of training:

Real, life, and natural situations

Students should be able to solve real communication problems:

- 1) thank you for the lesson - "Thank you for the lesson".
- 2) offer help - "Can I help you?"
- 3) clarify your homework - "What was your home task?"

4) complain about a snitch, an abuser - "He's been telling on me! He is a sneak".

Real communication begins with Classroom English.

The competence approach is an objective phenomenon in education. The implementation of the competence approach in the training of future foreign language teachers is conditioned by the accelerating global processes of globalization and informatization. The concept of "professional competence of a teacher" expresses the unity of theoretical and practical readiness in the integral structure of the individual and characterizes his professionalism. In the structure of professional competence of a teacher, professional-content, professional-activity and professional-personal components are distinguished. The professional-content, or basic, component assumes that the teacher has theoretical knowledge, which ensures awareness when determining the content of the teacher's professional activity. The professional-activity, or practical, component includes professional knowledge and skills tested in action, mastered by the individual as the most effective. The professional and personal component includes professional and personal qualities that determine the position and orientation of the teacher as a person, individual and subject of activity.

Communicative English language teaching should be of an activity-based nature. The use of the communicative teaching method in the training of future English teachers should be based on the following basic principles:

(1) speech orientation. Learning English should be done through communication. Of particular importance in the training of future English teachers is the formation of their communicative competence. The basis of

communicative competence is linguistic competence;

(2) functional orientation. The functionality of teaching is provided by the communicative, functionally adequate behavior of the teacher and students. This principle assumes that students are aware of the functionality of all aspects of the language being studied;

(3) situationality. Communication training is based on situations. Situations are considered as a system of relationships. This is an integrative dynamic system of social status, role, activity and moral relationships of the subjects of communication;

(4) novelty. It manifests itself in various components of the lesson. This is the novelty of speech situations; the novelty of using the material (its awareness). Novelty ensures the rejection of arbitrary memorization of statements, dialogues, texts, etc., develops speech production, heuristics and productivity of students' speech skills, arouses interest in educational and cognitive activities;

(5) personal orientation of communication. Personal orientation allows you to take into account the individual parameters inherent in the individual. It causes students to be truly motivated. This is both a general need-based communication motivation and a situational one;

(6) simulation. The content of the educational aspect is provided by modeling the content side of communication in various activities. The content side of communication is made up of problems, selected taking into account the age and individual interests of students, as well as their activities and inter-subject relationships. The simulation is based on exercises. Thus, when preparing a competent English teacher, it is necessary to implement a truly communicative teaching of communication in this language and proceed from the basic principles of this method.

The State Standard of Education and the Concept of Modernization of Education distinguish the competence approach as one of the most significant. The competence approach is a set of general principles for determining the goals of education, selecting the content of education, organizing the educational process, and evaluating educational results.

K. D. Ushinsky emphasized that the teacher should not be limited to the acquired knowledge. It is very important to develop the teacher's ability and willingness to constantly expand their scientific and pedagogical horizons. The teacher teaches successfully as long as he learns himself.

A real teacher is obliged to work on the future, to be ahead of his time. He should not be concerned with a single individual, but with the world of people. Thanks to this, the teaching profession becomes a creative mission. The teacher's mission is not only his own interests, motives, and plans. He is an intermediary between those who are learning and the system of ideas, traditions, and culture of his people and humanity. His duty is to educate worthy people who are able to multiply the achievements of human civilization.

The process of forming a competent specialist is one of the main problems of pedagogy. In recent years, the teacher's competence has become increasingly relevant due to the fact that social experience is constantly being transformed, the field of education is being reconstructed, all kinds of author programs of pedagogical systems are appearing, and the level of social orders for a specialist is increasing.

Due to the fact that society is becoming more open, with the development and further strengthening of international, political, economic, and cultural ties, the process of forming a real social order with regard to

foreign languages is taking place. The question of improving the quality of training of future specialists in a foreign language becomes relevant.

The main goal of teacher training is the acquisition of skills in the field of special disciplines. General pedagogy, didactics, psychology, linguistics, sociolinguistics, semiotics, logic – this is not a complete list of sciences that determine the professional competence of a teacher/teacher of foreign languages.

A decisive role in the theoretical training of the future teacher of foreign languages is played by knowledge of the basic provisions of linguistics, "scientific grammar", the science of " ... which most moves us forward to the knowledge of the ways in which our thinking is possible independently clearly (clearly) understand your own actions", a science that occupies a special position in the hierarchy of sciences and that is interested in a very special object-language.

There are seven key educational competencies:

1. Value-semantic competence. This is a competence in the field of worldview, associated with the student's value ideas, his ability to see and understand the world around him, to navigate in it, to realize his role and purpose, to be able to choose target and semantic settings for his actions and actions, to make decisions. The individual educational trajectory of the student and the program of his life activity as a whole depend on it.

2. General cultural competence – a range of issues in which the student must be well-informed, have knowledge and experience of activity. These are the features of national and universal culture, the spiritual and moral foundations of human life and humanity, individual peoples, the cultural foundations of family, social, social

phenomena and traditions, the role of science and religion in human life, their impact on the world, competence in the household and cultural and leisure sphere, for example, the possession of effective ways of organizing free time.

3. Educational and cognitive competence. This is a set of competencies of the student in the field of independent cognitive activity, including elements of logical, methodological, general educational activities, correlated with real cognizable objects. This includes knowledge and skills of goal-setting, planning, analysis, reflection, self-assessment of educational and cognitive activities. Within this competence, the requirements of the corresponding functional literacy are determined: the ability to distinguish facts from speculation, the possession of measurement skills, the use of probabilistic, statistical and other methods of cognition.

4. Information competence. With the help of real objects (TV, tape recorder, telephone, fax, computer, printer, modem, copier) and information technologies (audio and video recording, e-mail, media, Internet), the ability to independently search, analyze and select the necessary information, organize, transform, save and transmit it is formed. This competence provides the student's activity skills with information contained in academic subjects and educational areas, as well as in the surrounding world.

5. Communicative competence includes knowledge of the necessary languages, ways of interacting with surrounding and remote people and events, skills of working in a group, knowledge of various social roles in a team. The student must be able to introduce himself, write a letter, a questionnaire, an application, ask a question, conduct a discussion, etc.

6. Social and labor competence means the possession of knowledge and experience in civil and public activities (performing the role of a citizen, observer, voter, representative), in the social and labor sphere (the rights of the consumer, buyer, customer, manufacturer), in the field of family relations and duties, in matters of economics and law, in professional self-determination. This competence includes, for example, the ability to analyze the situation in the labor market, to act in accordance with personal and public benefit, to possess the ethics of labor and civil relations. The student learns the minimum necessary skills for life in modern society, social activity and functional literacy.

7. The competence of personal self-improvement is aimed at mastering the methods of physical, spiritual and intellectual self-development, emotional self-regulation and self-support. The real object here is the student himself. He masters the ways of working in his own interests and opportunities, which is expressed in his continuous self-knowledge, the development of personal qualities necessary for a modern person, the formation of psychological literacy, a culture of thinking and behavior. This competence includes the rules of personal hygiene, taking care of one's own health, sexual literacy, and internal environmental culture. This also includes a set of qualities related to the basics of safe life.

In conclusion, the use of the competence approach makes it possible for the comprehensive harmonious development of the future English language teachers' personality, the development of mutual responsibility, to improve the quality of training based on the development of educational standards, the development of research skills in the learning process, and the preparation of the educational base for further training.

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